

Studies on Some Less Familiar Ferrocyanogen Complex. Part IX. Electrometric studies on the interaction of Mo(III) with Potassium Ferricyanide

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Of the three electrometric methods, viz, conductometry, potentiometry and amperometry, employed for studying the interaction between Mo(III) and potassium ferricyanide, the latter two could be successfully used in determining the composition of the reaction products. Inflection points indicate the possibility of the existence of the redox system $\text{Mo}^{3+} + \text{FeCy}_6^{3-} \rightleftharpoons \text{Mo}^{4+} + \text{FeCy}_6^{4-}$ during the course of the reaction and the formation of compounds of the type $(\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}} \text{Fe}^{\text{II}} \text{Cy}_6)^{2-}$ or $\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}} \text{Fe}^{\text{II}} \text{Cy}_6$ could be envisaged on the basis of these studies.

Investigations on the ferrocyanogen complexes of molybdenum present a number of difficulties. These are (i) the non-availability of the salts of the metal in the pure form (and if so in a few isolated cases, there is lack of authenticity regarding the chemical representation), (ii) the existence of aggregated ions in the solution of their salts, (iii) the colloidal nature of the reaction products, thereby making their isolation and subsequent analysis difficult, (iv) the existence of the redox potential in the system

decomposition of the acidified solutions of potassium ferro- and ferricyanides by molybdenum salts. It appears that the factors enumerated above had been mainly responsible in not providing a clear picture of the real nature and composition of these complexes. Very few references, worth mentioning, are available in the existing literature. These are of Barbieri¹ who analysed the precipitate obtained by the interaction of ammonium molybdate and potassium ferrocyanide ($\text{NH}_4 \cdot \text{FeCy}_6 \cdot 2\text{MoO}_3$) and of Pani and Rao² on the conductometric titrations of molybdic acid and potassium ferrocyanide.

The product obtained by the electrolytic reduction of molybdic acid is said to constitute mainly of molybdenum ions in their trivalent state. A study of the interaction of this compound with potassium ferro- and ferricyanides was thought worth undertaking due to the following reasons. Firstly, the reduction product is probably the only compound where Mo(III) exists in a purely cationic form and is fairly stable in solution, secondly, the ferrocyanogen complexes of Mo(III) have not yet been reported in the existing literature and hence an elucidation of their composition would be quite interesting. The present communication deals with investigations on Mo(III) ferricyanides using electrometric methods. Attempts to study the interaction of this metal ion with potassium ferrocyanide met with little success since of the three methods employed, only conductometric method appeared to be of some use. The inflection points were, however, not sharp enough to furnish any clue to the composition of the complex formed or the factors influencing the reaction itself.

1. *Ber.*, 1927, 60B, 2415.

2. *Curr. Sci.*, 1953, 22, 237.

EXPERIMENTAL

Solutions of potassium ferricyanide was prepared and standardised as described earlier³. Mo(III) solution was prepared by the method recommended by Chilesott⁴. 4.3% Molybdc acid solution in (4*N* HCl) was taken in a porous pot and electrolysed between a platinum plate (4 cm² area) anode and a bright platinum gauze (12.4 cm² area) cathode at a current density of 0.5 amp. cm⁻², using a Fischer electro-analyser. The reduction of Mo(VI) was completed in about 2.5 hrs: the green solution first obtained changed finally to reddish brown. The strength of the solution was determined potentiometrically by titrating against KMnO₄ of known strength.

Potentiometric titrations were carried out with the help of a Tinsley potentiometer (Type 3387B) with lamp and scale arrangement. A bright platinum electrode was used as the indicator and a saturated calomel electrode as the reference. In some cases FeCy₆³⁻ + e ⇌ FeCy₆⁴⁻ couple (obtained by dipping bright platinum electrode in a solution of potassium ferricyanide containing minute quantity of potassium ferrocyanide) was employed during these titrations.

Amperometric studies were carried out in a manner described earlier by Malik⁵. Titrations between Mo(III) and K₃FeCy₆ were carried out at 0.0 volt since a limiting current was realised at this voltage in the case of K₃FeCy₆. 0.1*M*-KCl as supporting electrolyte and 0.01% gelatin were used as maximum suppressor.

Conductometric titrations were carried out by conductivity bridge (No. L-350140) using conductivity cell of K=0.1, No. L-356698 (Cambridge Instrument Co.) Fairly concentrated solutions of the titrant were used to avoid volume correction. The results are summarised in Table I-III.

TABLE I
Mo(III)-K₃FeCy₆ potentiometric titrations reaction

I. Direct (Fig. 1) at FeCy ₆ ³⁻ + e ⇌ FeCy ₆ ⁴⁻ couple.		
Vol. and con. in the cell.	Vol. of 0.1 <i>M</i> Mo (III) from the curve.	Combining ratio Mo (III): K ₃ FeCy ₆ from the inflection point.
K ₃ FeCy ₆ .		
20 ml of 4.0 × 10 ⁻² <i>M</i>	8.00 ml	1 : 1
20 " 2.0 × 10 ⁻²	3.6	0.9 : 1
20 " 1.0 × 10 ⁻²	1.85	0.92 : 1
II. Reverse (Fig. 2).		
Mo (III).		
20 ml of 4 × 10 ⁻² <i>M</i>	8.4 ml	1 : 1.05
20 " 2 × 10 ⁻²	3.8	1 : 0.95
20 " 1 × 10 ⁻²	2.2	1 : 1.00
III. Direct (Fig. 3) without employing FeCy ₆ ⁴⁻ ⇌ FeCy ₆ ³⁻ + e couple.		
K ₃ FeCy ₆		
20 ml of 2 × 10 ⁻² <i>M</i>	3.8 ml	0.95 : 1
20 " 1 × 10 ⁻²	2.2	1.10 : 1
IV. Reverse (Fig. 4) without employing FeCy ₆ ³⁻ + e ⇌ FeCy ₆ ⁴⁻ couple.		
Mo (III)		
20 ml of 2 × 10 ⁻² <i>M</i>	3.5 ml	1 : 0.99
20 " 1 × 10 ⁻²	1.8	1 : 0.9

3. This *Journal*, 1961, 38, 312.

4. *Z. Elektrochem.*, 1906, 12, 1946, 1731.

5. This *Journal*, 1961, 38, 301.

TABLE II

Amperometric titrations between Mo(III) and K₃FeCy₆

Vol. and conc. of in the cell K ₃ FeCy ₆	Direct titrations (Fig. 5)	
	Vol. from the curve 0.1M-Mo(III)	Combining ratio Mo(III) : K ₃ FeCy ₆ from the inflection point.
20 ml. 1×10 ⁻² M	2.0 ml	1 : 1
20 0.75×10 ⁻²	1.5	1 : 1
20 0.5 ×10 ⁻²	1.0	1 : 1

Typical curve shown in Fig. 5.

MO(III)		Reverse titrations (Fig. 6)	
Vol.	Conc.	Vol.	Conc.
20 ml.	1.00×10 ⁻² M	2.0 cc	0.1M- K ₃ FeCy ₆
20	0.75×10 ⁻²	1.5	
20 cc	0.50×10 ⁻²	1.0	

Typical curve shown in Fig. 6.

TABLE III

Direct conductometric titrations between Mo(III) and K₃FeCy₆.

Vol. and conc. of K ₃ FeCy ₆ in the cell.	Vol. of 0.1M Mo(III) from the curve.	Combining ratio Mo(III): K ₃ FeCy ₆ from the inflection point.
40 ml of 5.0×10 ⁻³ M	2.0 ml	1 : 1
40 2.5×10 ⁻³	1.0	1 : 1
40 1.25×10 ⁻³	0.5	1 : 1

Reverse titrations (Mo (III) in the cell) could not be carried out due to high conductance of MoCl₃ solution.

DISCUSSION

The conductometric titrations between Mo(III) and K₃FeCy₆ could not be carried out very satisfactorily since sharp breaks in the titration curves could not be realised. It

Fig. 1 Direct Potentiometric titration between Mo(III) and K₃FeCy₆ at FeCy₆³⁻+e ⇌ FeCy₆⁴⁻ couple. 20 c.c. 1×10⁻² M K₃FeCy₆ against 0.1 M Mo(III).

may be partly due to the high conductance of MoCl_3 solution and partly due to the formation of colloidal aggregates during the course of the reaction. Such factors do not interfere in the potentiometric and amperometric titrations and sharp breaks (Figs. 1 to 6) are realised both for direct (K_3FeCy_6 in the cell) and reverse titrations (MoCl_3 in the cell). Another interesting aspect of these titrations is that the potentiometric titrations could be carried out without employing a $\text{FeCy}_6^{4-} \rightleftharpoons \text{FeCy}_6^{3-} + e$ indicator electrode (which is usually employed in studying metal ferrocyanide complexes). It has been found that typical potentiometric curves are obtained with (Fig. 1 & 2) and without (Fig. 3 & 4) using the electrodes.

FIG. 2 Reverse Potentiometric titration betn. K_3FeCy_6 and Mo(III) .

20 c.c. $4 \times 10^{-2} M$ Mo(III) against $0.1 M$ K_3FeCy_6 .

FIG. 3. Direct Potentiometric titration betn. Mo(III) and K_3FeCy_6 .

20 c.c. $2 \times 10^{-2} M$ K_3FeCy_6 against $1.1 M$ Mo(III) .

From the inflection point an approximate combining ratio of 1:1 for the reactants is obtained.

The reaction can be written in the following ways:

or

In view of the fact that in the reaction mixture of both Mo^{3+} and FeCy_6^{3-} are present, which in turn are endowed with reducing and oxidising properties respectively, it is quite likely that the redox potential of the system would influence the whole course of the reaction, resulting in the formation of the complexes $\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{Fe}^{\text{II}}\text{Cy}_6$ or $\text{Mo}^{\text{IV}}\text{OFe}^{\text{II}}\text{Cy}_6^{2-}$ instead of $\text{Mo}^{\text{III}}\text{Fe}^{\text{III}}\text{Cy}_6$. The view finds support in the fact that potentiometric titrations between Mo(III) and FeCy_6^{3-} could be performed without employing the indicator electrode $\text{FeCy}_6^{3-} + e \rightleftharpoons \text{FeCy}_6^{4-}$ (usually employed in studying metal ferrocyanogen complexes).

FIG. 4. Reverse Potentiometric titration betn. Mo(III) and K_3FeCy_6 .
30 c.c. $2 \times 10^{-2} M$ Mo(III) against 0.1M K_3FeCy_6 .

FIG. 5. Direct Amperometric titration betn. Mo(III) and K_3FeCy_6 .
20 c.c. $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ K_3FeCy_6 against 0.1M Mo(III)

Fig. 6. Reverse Amperometric titration betn. Mo(III) against K_3FeCy_6 .
20 c.c. $0.5 \times 10^{-2} M$ Mo(III) against 0.1M K_3FeCy_6 .

As to whether the complex $Mo^{IV} Fe^{II}Cy_6$ or $Mo^{IV} OFe^{II}Cy_6$ is formed, the possibility of the latter appears to be less in view of the high acidic content of Mo^{3+} solution.

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